

Genre fantasy and detective: scientific interpretation in theoretical views in the world biliteracy (belles-lettres)

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Key words

fantasy, fiction, detective, legal detective, legal thriller science fiction, myth, romance, fairy tale, image.

Annotation

This study aims to provide a scientific analysis of the fantasy and detective genres which have entered literature as a new literary term. Every nation introduces a new term or a new literary genre into its literature, realizes its essence, and then tries to reconcile it with its culture. Fantasy and detective as a literary genre today is incomparable with its place in world literature. In the study, fantasy is analyzed as the main fictional genre in the literature and its meaning with some scientific approaches. It also explores the characteristics of the fiction and fantasy genres that are still ongoing. Then it determines the relationship between them based on scientific considerations.

Introduction

There have been conducted many studies on Uzbek folk tales and mythology by Uzbek literary scholars. However, today the appearance of a new literary phenomenon combining such epic genres is great news for Uzbek writers. Fantasy and detective are not a genre that has arisen today; its roots go back to the distant past. However, many scholars initially viewed it as a direction of fiction. For example, M. S. Galina [1] and E. N. Kovtun [2] to fantasy as a "genre", A. Karelin - the "subgenre" of fiction [3], A. I. Osipov - "direction" [4] is called. Such theoretical considerations have been ongoing up until today.

The word "fantasy" (English fantasy - "fantasy") is used in modern science fiction in two intersecting meanings. In a narrow sense, fantasy has a fabulously mythological prose genre adventure, usually a character, The second half of the XIX - the first half of the XX century. Close parallel phenomena were in the literary process of Germany and the Scandinavian countries, where from the middle of the 20th century. Original versions of

the same genre developed. Within this framework, the even narrower concept of "genre fantasy" is distinguished. This, the most massive and demanded by the market, the direction reproduces more or less the topics and the plot moves of the classic works of early fantasy. The samples are usually the "Lord of the Rings" (1954-1955) by J. R. R. Tolkien, (1892-1973) - the so-called epic fantasy, as well as adventure stories R. I. Howard (1906-1936) - "Heroic fantasy." The wider meaning of the word "fantasy" covers all directions of "unscientific" fiction, including a powerful stream of mystical prose and "horror" (Horror), whose story goes back to the era of romanticism.

Detective fiction is a subgenre of crime fiction and mystery fiction in which an investigator or a detective—whether professional, amateur or retired—investigates a crime, often murder. The detective genre began around the same time as speculative fiction and other genre fiction in the mid-nineteenth century and has remained extremely popular, particularly in novels.[1] Some of the most famous heroes of detective

fiction include C. Auguste Dupin, Sherlock Holmes, and Hercule Poirot. Juvenile stories featuring The Hardy Boys, Nancy Drew, and The Boxcar Children have also remained in print for several decades.

Objectives of the Study

An analysis of based on these goals, we will conduct our study with the following objectives. – to analysis of the phenomenon of fantasy and its origins.

- to identify the features and commonality of fantasy and fiction.
- to study of the primary and the secondary world fantasy works.
- to analysis of the images system in fantasy works.

The result of the study will be beneficial for the World literature department and English Literature teachers in general.

Method

Fantasy is still a mysterious question for scientists, which does not require a solid solution. The ideas expressed by various researchers occur the confusion inherent in fantasy. There are many points of view that relate to the theory of fantasy. On the essence of fantasy and its content, scientists Tsvetan Todorov, Katherine Hume, Mark Bauld, Rosemary Jackson, Irenush Opatsky, Colin Menlav, Jones D.V., Yakovenko O.K., Chernysheva T. O, Chepur E. A., Frumkin K., Stroeve K., Neelov E.M., Laksman R., Krinitsyna O.P., Kovtun E.N., Kaplan V., Gopman V. L. Britikov A.F., Berezin V., Baturin D. A., [7] who brought his scientific views to the phenomena fantasy and fiction. Polish literary critic Ireneusz Opacki noted that if the conditions in which writers live in the history of the development of the genre change, literature will also change, including new topics, motives and problems of the time. There is great interest in the principle of psychoanalytic among fantasy researchers. It is in this context that many scholars reject the distinction between the literary style for "fantasy" and the psychoanalytic term for "phantasy.". It leads to a combination of psychoanalytic theory and style form. In this regard, the Gothic works of modernists and postmodernists were carefully analyzed in their research of stories. The introduction of fantasy as a new phenomenon in Uzbek literature in the course of our research, of course, requires a study of its essence. In this regard, we explore the commonality and features of the components of this genre, as well as fiction, as well as theoretical approaches of scientists.

Instrument and Analysis Procedure

This research is mainly used as an introduction of new term fantasy in Uzbek literature and a source of much theoretical knowledge about it. It also makes read the fictional books and improve the reading skills of our youth. Fan readers or students are get acquainted with this genre completely and find more interesting to read many works that written on basis of the fantasy genre. In Uzbek literature, so far only information about the genre of fiction and its features is provided. This study is one of the main sources for revealing the characteristics of the fantasy and science fiction genres. The understanding of the key aspects of these two genres is presented in tabular form, which allows teachers of world literature to use them as the main guide in all lessons.

Results and Discussion

Scientific approaches to origin of Fantasy genre (I)

Fantasy has been developing since the end of the 19th century. It is impossible to put fantasy into an exact model of the system. We face with epics, myths, works in the spirit of love, satire, historical works, utopian tales, folk tales and parables, which are often found in fantasy. We can continue this list in more detail, but only they can serve as the basis for our study of the historical stages of the development of fantasy. It is very important to study them at the stage of development of modern fantasy literature. The use of various small epic genres in modern fantasy creates means of enriching diversity and imagination in it. This allows distinguishing it from traditional genres. However, it did not develop as a clearly distinguishable term. Thus, the terms "fiction" and "fantasy" have retained their interchangeable forms. This led to a controversy as to whether fantasy literature matches the form of another genre.

In modern literature, this allows us to include in the concept of "fantasy" (first of all, English -speaking literary critics) such phenomena as the direction of the implicitly mystical prose of "Fantastique" or a variety of magical realism in French literature. In Romanesque and Slavic countries, literary critics and critics, as a rule, use the term fantasy only to fantasy in the narrow sense or even only to genre fantasy. Sometimes, thereby consciously emphasizes its "alien" – English – origin. On the other hand, the tradition of calling works of fantastic literature in general "Fantasies" – Fantasy – dates back

to the beginning XIX century after the isolation of science fiction by the beginning of the XX century. The term was naturally inherited by the fiction of the "unscientific" in its various hypostases. The closest analogue of the English Fantasy in this expansion sense is the Russian "Literature of Fiction".

J. R. R. Tolkien dedicated the essay "On Magic Stories" (1947). Tolkien has fantasy as the ability to unlimited creative fiction—a means of creating a "magical story". Fantasy leads a person out of everyday life to the vastness of a magical country, extravaganza. Creating a "magical story", a person freely or involuntarily creates a whole "secondary world", inevitably similar to "primary", but existing in his own, not at all rational laws. This secondary world may well be placed somewhere in mythical

The world of "primary", and even adjacent to it in the present - as the world of ancient fairy tales and a heroic epic. "Magic story" is a way of liberation, escape from dysfunctional reality. The escape (Escape) is a significant topic of both the mentioned Tolkien essay and many works of both intercessors and critics of fantasy. Fantasy, undoubtedly, is the literature "escapade", challenging the current being. "Magic stories" Tolkien considered "serious", adult literature. In his opinion, "childishness" and a naive morality conjugated with it, coupled with excessive softness, are

destructive for genuine "magical history". By the way, he noticed that at the heart of "childhood" is a perspicuous idea of children's tastes. Be that as it may, it is here that the feature between the "magical history" and "magical", "fairing" fairy tale (Fairy-Tale, Conte de Fee), usual for English and French literature of the XIX-early XX century. The escapade nature of the fantasy in this, "narrow" sense clearly blocks it from the literature of horrors. Fantasy worlds, of course, can be terrible and dangerous. But usually by themselves they are not called to push away, but are obliged to attract, attract their reader. In addition, the horror literature as a whole should not deal with the "secondary", but with our "primary" world, in which incomprehensible, unnatural forces burst. This is a mystical feature fiction (English Supernatural Fiction) in general. So, although the "border" works of fantasy and horror account is considerable, distinguished in its pure form is quite simple.

The origin of the modern type fantasy in the UK is associated with the names of G. Macdonald, (1824–1905) and W. Morris, (1834–1895). The first created a new standard for a children's fairy tale, saturating it with epic pathos and philosophical content. The trend of rapprochement between the "children's" and "adult" literature was further developed in the work of L. Carroll (1832–1898), J. M. Barrie, (1860–1937) and other religious Romans McDonald's parables can be considered as

one of the first experiments of building the "secondary world". Morris is the author of the epic series - adventure novels whose action takes place in conditional the Middle Ages, which has become a model for the later fantasy.

The next stage in the development of the British fantasy is represented by Lord Dunsany, (1878-1957), W. H. Hodgson, (1877-1918), D. Lindsay, (1878-1945) and nearby) and nearby) other authors. Dunsany was the first to cast a genre in a completely independent literary form, separating and from the literary fairy tale addressed to children, and from a romantic pseudo-historical novel. The key innovation was the creation of a "secondary world" completely autonomous from the well-known historical and modern reality, with its own cosmology that exists in "its right". Hodgson in the novel "The Night Land" (1912) first embodied the literary model of genre fantasy: the hero's quest against the background of the developed "secondary world" revealed over the vicissitudes of the quest. In Lindsay's novel "A Voyage to Arcturus" (1920) first used "scientific" fantastic the eyeballs as a basis for own mythological and cosmological constructions. This line - the conditional placement of the "secondary" mythological worlds on a different planet - found a continuation in the work of E. R. Edson, (1882-1945). Edson's novels, saturated by linguistic experimentation, original philosophical and aesthetic ideas, had a noticeable effect on the final folding of fantasy standards.

The latter is associated with the predominant names of J. R. R. Tolkien and C. S. Lewis, (1898-1963) - members of the Oxfords of the literary circle "Inklings". Tolkien's novel "The Lord of the Rings" was the first world bestseller among the works of the genre. The fantastic world of the Mediterranean, created by the author on the material of the German-Scandinavian myths, was bred in it, has become a model for thousands of imitations.

At the same time, in terms of development and "literary authenticity", Tolkien's myth-making remains an unsurpassed peak of the genre. The works of Lewis became the most noticeable in the XX century. The phenomenon of "Christian fantasy", combining elements of various fantastic genres, religious parables or even theological work. Among the most prominent authors of the British fantasy of the middle of the XX century. It also refers to M. Peake, (1911-1968), the author of the philosophical fantastic trilogy about the castle of Gormengast. Of the later authors, R. Adams (1920), which combined the style of fantasy with the images of a

traditional animal fairy tale, can be distinguished.

The fantasy raises the storyteller L. Baum (1846-1915), the author of the Lake Country, and the most popular pseudo-nuclear science fiction writer E. R. Burroughs, (1875-1950) are considered. The latter was the forefront of the heyday in the United States "heroic fantasy", the most a noticeable representative of which was R.I. Howard. Howard belonged to the literary circle of the "father" of the modern literature of H. P. Lovecraft, (1890-1937). The gloomy phantasmagoria of Lovecraft significantly influenced many authors of the early American fantasy: such S. A. Smith, (1893-1961), F. Pratt (1897-1956), F. Leiber, (1910-1992).

Many of them are characterized by the use of "scientific" fantastic alien or futuristic settings. A. Van Vogt, (1912-2000), J. Vance also continued by Barrose. (J. Vance, p. 1916), L. Brackett (1915-1978). Such a mixture of genres is called Science Fantasy. The ancestor of the "ironic fantasy", using the genre for satire and parody itself, was J. B. Cabell, (1879-1958). From the middle of the XX century. In the United States, the impact of the British "epic fantasy" penetrates. Its influence was reflected in the fantasy work of A. Norton (1912-2005), L. Alexander, (1924-2007), U. Le Guin, (1929), etc. Confirmed thanks to Tolkien and Lewis in the middle of the XX century. In the genre fantasy "conservatism" with clear criteria of morality, the opposition of good and evil, and Christian allusions caused a protest in the form of the appearance of the so-called new wave.

The Anglo-American writer M. Moorcock, (1939) was its leader and theorist. In his work, he resolutely mixes and revives the images of both epic and heroic fantasy. Already in the 70s of the XX century. The production of fantasy is increasingly subordinate to the laws of the market - the era of "commodity fantasy" begins (term U. Le Guin). The vast majority with the produced genre-based producing genre is consciously epigone character, repeating the known samples. This does not exclude, of course, individual or noticeable in literary terms, but new templates are usually quickly formed on the basis of these phenomena. The latest example is the cycle of J. Rowling, (1965) about Harry Potter. In Romanesque, Slavic and other literature, imitative fantasy develops. It borrows from English-speaking samples often not only the construction of plots, but also specific images dating back to German-Scandinavian mythology and folklore.

Fiction (detective) and Fantasy (II)

As a community between science fiction

and fantasy, we can point to the human mind as the most fundamental factor. Because a person can discover any reality for himself and unwittingly discover a new world rich in miracles. In fiction, a being that arises in the human mind demonstrates reciprocity with fantasy. Today, the genre of "fiction" and works based on it, play an important role in world literature. Scientists who have studied the genre and its problematic aspects have linked its introduction to the literary environment in connection with the term "fiction" with the article by Charles Nod of 1830 "About Fantastic Literature". In this article, Sh. Node interprets it under private science fiction, as fictional or unreal content. Some researchers believe that Ts. Todorov is one of the founders of the genre of fiction, a phenomenon between doubt and supernatural concepts that can never be solved. "In the universe, we know one thing: there are no demons, effeminate creatures, or bloodthirsty creatures in the world; where events are not explained by the same familiar laws of the universe. A person caught in a whirlpool of events must choose one of two solutions. Let him become a victim of both the magic of feelings and a product of imagination - the laws of the universe are respected as they are; In the end, the event does occur, it becomes an integral part of the being, but after a while the being is controlled by unknown laws..." [15].

In my opinion, Todorov in his description formed structural features in the text. At the

same time, the reader becomes indecisive. Todorov tries to solve the problem, taking into account the doubts of the reader: "Fiction ... means immersing the reader in the world of images. This world is determined by the reader's dubious assumptions about the events being told. It should be noted that in our brain there is no active reader, but the role of the reader in the text is noticeable." [15] Todorov cites two conditions for a remarkable piece of fiction in his research. One of them is the general condition, indicating a feature of work experience and expressing suspicion. Another - the reader accepts the text and rejects allegory, as well as artistic interpretation. Although the rejection of allegory (metaphor) was approved by some theoretical researchers, Todorov's opinion was not fully accepted. This implies not only the adoption of a metaphor but also the interpretation of its full meaning by Todorov, emphasizing its necessity. According to French fiction, "Meaning of Fiction" by Roger Kayua "Fiction - is not a change in reality in a world without a miracle, but an influence on a circle that contradicts the inevitable laws of some impossible creature" [16]. Researcher R. Ibragimova said: "The fantastic theme is almost no different from the real one. The difference between them is that we imagine that one and the same event really exists or does not exist" [17]. Thus, the miracle of fiction is not to change the whole reality, but to a certain extent affect the laws of the existing universe. Fiction takes place in literature as a

genre, which, in turn, serves as the basis for small epic genres or elements in its composition. For example, we also encounter various fabulous or mythological images or plots in the genre of fiction that make up the composition of fantasy. It follows that the combination of fiction and fantasy in terms of content creates aspects of mutual similarity between the two genres.

Conclusions

When we analyze the fantasy and detective mentioned in our study and its genesis based on the scientific views of various scientists, it can be recognized as an important new term for Uzbek literature. The fantasy and detective origin is first analyzed separately from the various epic genres that make up its component, namely myths, fairy tales, and chivalric novels, and as a result of their imagination and stages of their development, they are subsequently analyzed

using scientifically based ideas, the emergence of fantasy through syncretism from the elements of fairy tales and chivalric (romance) novels is scientifically justified. Fantasy works that reflect Western culture have commented on various views on their social life and the structure of society. There are also scientific views on the use of magic through various images in European medieval government and the formation of fantasy legends of King Arthur as a genre. By the twentieth century, attention had been paid to the fantasy genre in world literature and general ideas about the features and commonality of fiction and fantasy works written and being written on their basis. There are also scientific hypotheses about the genre of fiction and its role in public life, and its specific elements are explained sequentially. In addition, there are opinions based on the scientific views of various foreign scientists who today conduct research in the genre of science fiction.

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